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Impact of a learning analytics dashboard on the practice of students and teachers

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports results of the deployment of a learning analytics dashboard in the context of introductory Maths, Physics and Chemistry courses in the first year of the Engineering bachelor of a Swiss technical university. Informed by research on self-regulated learning, learning analytics dashboards and the social practice of learning in Higher Education, the tool includes a learning diary feature where students report their progress and the difficulties encountered in solving the course exercises. Both students and teachers have access to a dashboard showing an overview of the class progress and difficulties, the student view including personalized feedback. We present usage and survey data, and show how these help to identify key intervention principles to maximize the impact of learning analytics dashboards on the practice of students and teachers.

1 INTRODUCTION

The ability to solve complex problems is essential for engineers and teaching problem solving is therefore important goal of engineering higher education [1]. Problem solving and problem solving teaching and learning have been the object of research for decades. There is broad agreement in the research [2, 3] that students actually need a number of different things in order to solve problems. In particular, alongside content knowledge of the discipline and strategies for solving problems, students need self-regulation strategies which include planning, monitoring and evaluation. For instance, students who, when solving a mathematical problem, start

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by analysing the problem and making a plan are demonstrating self-regulated learning behaviours. This is also the case of students who, after solving a problem, analyse their solution to assess whether it is reasonable. Self-regulation strategies have been shown to differentiate expert behaviour from novice behaviour and to be key in the ability of students to solve previously unseen problems, where they need to “create” the solution method [2].

Students can be helped to develop self-regulated learning (SRL) and training for self-regulated learning has been in place for many years. Elements of such training are self-reflection questions, in particular questions which help students to self-assess their own performance [4]. Approaches such as “exam wrappers” [5] for instance, use postexam self-reporting questionnaires to draw students’ attention to the feedback they received, to guide them in the analysis of their difficulties and to lead them to evaluate the adequacy of their learning strategies. Learning diaries [6] are another example of self-regulated learning intervention where students fill-out self-reporting questionnaires regularly over a period of time.

With the development of online learning environments, research on and tools for developing SRL have also gone online and joined with the learning analytics community. In this context, learning analytics dashboards (LADs), which present learning analytics data visually to the user, are researched as a way to present actionable feedback to students [7]. LADs can and have been used to present students with self-reported data from self-regulated learning questionnaires [8]. However, as many authors point out (see [9] for instance), little empirical research has been carried out so far on whether such tools actually have an impact on learning and even less on whether they have impact on the *practice* of its users.

In order to help engineering students develop their self-regulated learning skills in relation to problem solving, we have developed a tool which combines an online learning diary and a learning analytics dashboard. After a pilot phase, the dashboard has been deployed and used during one semester in introductory Maths, Physics and Chemistry courses in the first year of the Engineering bachelor of a Swiss technical university. This paper presents a study of the impact of this dashboard on the practice of its users. After presenting the dashboard and the literature on which it draws, we describe the research method, present results and discuss their implications.

2 RELATED WORK

2.1 Self-regulated learning (SRL)

Self-regulated learning can be defined as “self-generated thoughts, feelings and actions that are systematically guided by personal learning goals” [10]. Teaching students self-regulated learning strategies has been shown to have a positive impact on learning, in particular when it is linked to the discipline in which they are to be used [11]. The mathematics learning diaries by Schmitz and Perels [6] are an

example of such a discipline-embedded SRL teaching intervention. It has recently been argued that one interesting area for development is the use of measurement tools for self-regulated learning as intervention tools [12]. Thought of in this way, the process of reflecting on one's self-regulated learning, through undertaking a task such as a learning diary or a self-report questionnaire can trigger students to adapt their practices and has already have some positive results [6].

2.2 Learning Analytics Dashboards (LADs)

Learning analytics dashboards “support users in collecting personal information about various aspects of their life, behaviour, habits, thoughts, and interest” and “help users to improve self-knowledge by providing tools for the review and analysis of their personal history” [9]. They can be considered effective tools to support SRL by allowing users to both reflect on their practice when collecting data and get feedback on their practice when visualizing their data [13]. However, as emphasized by recent reviews [7, 9], LADs are usually deployed at small scale (less than 100 students / teachers) and few are used in authentic settings such as real courses. The impact of such tools on the actual practice of students and teachers in a real scale educational context has therefore seldom been studied.

3 THE DASHBOARD

Drawing on principles from the fields of SRL and LADs, the tool acts both as a diary and as a dashboard for students, and as a dashboard only for teachers.

3.1 Learning diary

The learning diary is designed to be filled out by students after they worked on the exercises and received some kind of feedback (e.g. feedback from a teaching assistant or written solution). It aims at engaging students in an active processing of the feedback they received in an after-exercise self-assessment activity.

Teachers setup the diary with a list of the different exercise sessions in the semester and, for each session, a list of exercises students are expected to solve. By completing a standard diary questionnaire for each exercise, students log the number of exercises they attempted, whether they succeeded or not as well as the difficulties they encountered in the process. The questionnaire includes a predefined list of difficulties which, while generic, relate to the quantitative type of problem solving that is specific to STEM disciplines. An example of a difficulty is: “I used the right method but I made calculation errors (arithmetic, algebraic, trigonometric, etc.)”. Part of the difficulties target the methodological aspects of the resolution. For instance, “I could not see how to start” relates to problem analysis, whereas “I tried a method and got stuck” relates to debugging. By targeting the link between lectures and exercises, other difficulties relate to the transfer aspects, such as “I had understood the course but I did not manage to apply it to the exercise”. In addition to the provided list, students can also enter their own difficulty in plain text if they want to. It is expected that, in filling out the questionnaire, students review each exercise

and clarify for themselves what their difficulties are. As discussed in the previous section, students should benefit from this first step of logging their data in the first place.

3.2 Dashboard

The student version of the dashboard is designed to show them: a) what kind of recurrent difficulties they are having, b) targeted advice designed to help them address their most common difficulties and c) how they compare to their class more generally in terms of the number of exercises they are completing and the difficulties they are experiencing. Presented both in a visual and textual format, this feedback and the associated recommendations are designed to help them identify and better target areas they should work on improving, in a deliberate practice approach.

The teacher version of the dashboard displays the same information as the student dashboard but at the level of the class only. For each exercise, the teacher can see: a) the proportion of students who tried the exercise, b) the proportion of students who succeeded or partially succeeded and c) the difficulties the class had with this exercise (see *Fig. 1*). This information helps to identify if students are struggling with understanding part of the course early. It therefore plays an important feedback role [13], allowing the teacher to adapt his/her teaching to address difficulties that students are having by, for example, clarifying links between lectures and exercises, giving advice on how to analyse a question or addressing particular mathematical weaknesses. In addition, the teacher can better judge the difficulty of exercises.

4 RESEARCH DESIGN

This study analyses the impact of the dashboard on the practice of students and teachers in terms of a) their use of the dashboard as recorded by the tool and b) the self-reported use and opinion of students on the dashboard.

Nine teachers volunteered to use the dashboard during the Autumn semester 2018-2019 in their courses for a total of N=1'786 registered students. Seven of the teachers were teaching obligatory courses, all of them worth 6 ECTS in the first year of the Bachelor curriculum: 4 in Physics, 2 in Maths and 1 in Chemistry. The two other teachers were teaching Humanities courses, one an optional course in Master (3 ECTS), the other an optional course given in the third year of Bachelor in another institution (5 ECTS). *Table 1* lists the different courses involved with their respective discipline, level and number of registered students. Teachers were given a user guide with a description of the type of information the dashboard could provide them, as well as a model presentation to introduce the tool to their students. They also received suggestions as to how to use it in the class but were free to use it the way they wanted.

Teachers and students have interacted with the dashboard over the 14 weeks of the semester. Usage data has been extracted from the dashboard at the end of the semester. In the last two weeks of the semester, a survey questionnaire has been

provided to teachers for a distribution in their classes. The survey asked students to self-report their use as well as the use of their teachers, to report on what motivated them to use it and on what they found useful in it, to give their opinion on its usability as well as the reasons why they eventually stopped using it.

Fig. 1. Dashboard view for teachers

Fig. 2. Relationship between student use and teacher use of the dashboard
 $\chi^2(8, N=190) = 21.7, p < .01$

Fig. 3. Relationship between student use and prompt to use the dashboard
Chi2 (16, N=347) = 263.3, p < .001

Fig. 4. Reasons to stop using the dashboard for students who learn from it (N=93)

5 DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

5.1 Overview

Table 1 summarizes the data collected for the different courses. The data extracted from the dashboard shows that it was used effectively in 7 of the 9 classes. We believe that the fact that the dashboard was not used by all the teachers who volunteered, illustrates the difficulty for them to make room in their practice for such a tool, even when they are highly motivated to do so. In terms of actual use of the dashboard by students, we see that the proportion varies between 11% and 94% of the students registered in the courses. We hypothesize that the way teachers integrate the use of the dashboard in their teaching plays an important role in the participation rate of students. Survey data was collected from 4 of the 7 classes who used the dashboard. In the following analysis, we will focus on these 4 courses as example case studies.

Table 1. Courses involved in the study.

Course	Discipline	Level	Number of students		
			Registered	Used the dashboard	Answered the survey
1	Physics	Bachelor 1 st year, 6 ECTS	203	64 (32%)	-
2	Chemistry	Bachelor 1 st year, 6 ECTS	275	64 (23%)	160 (58%)

3	Physics	Bachelor 1 st year, 6 ECTS	278	30 (11%)	-
4	Maths	Bachelor 1 st year, 6 ECTS	273	72 (26%)	101 (37%)
5	Humanities	Master, 3 ECTS	61	-	-
6	Maths	Bachelor 1 st year, 6 ECTS	260	-	-
7	Physics	Bachelor 1 st year, 6 ECTS	190	110 (58%)	71 (37%)
8	Physics	Bachelor 1 st year, 6 ECTS	229	33 (14%)	-
9	Humanities	Bachelor 3 rd year, 5 ECTS External Institution	17	16 (94%)	15 (88%)
TOTAL			1'786	389 (22%)	347 (19%)

5.2 Usage data

Overall, courses had an average of 45 exercises set up in the dashboard but with an important variation, from 4 to 118 exercises per course. Exercises were organized in sessions of around 6 exercises on average, with again an important variation from 1 to 13 exercises per session, thus illustrating the variety of the teaching contexts and pedagogical approaches represented in this study.

Table 2 presents the setup of the 4 case study courses and the respective number of students responses submitted to the dashboard. It is worth noting that 37 students were registered in more than one course, so the numbers of students cannot be assumed unique. The average participation of students, i.e. the number of responses they recorded over the number of exercises available in the dashboard related to the number of students in the course, varies between 10% and 98%. This number represents how active students were in using the dashboard, taking into account the amount of participation expected by the teacher. For example, a participation of 98% means that almost all students recorded their work on almost all the exercises set up by the teacher. The number of exercises to log in the diary seem to play a role in the activity of students on the dashboard but we hypothesize that the way teachers integrate the use of the dashboard in their teaching is an important moderator.

Table 2. Setup and student participation in the dashboard for the 4 case studies.

Course	Number of sessions	Number of exercises	Number of submissions	Average number of submissions per exercise	Average number of submissions per student	Average participation of students
2	13	118	780	6.61	12.19	10%
4	6	55	933	16.96	12.96	24%
7	8	43	1'022	23.77	9.29	22%
9	4	4	63	15.75	3.94	98%

5.3 Survey data

A total of N=347 students filled out the survey questionnaire. On the question “Did you use the exercise tracking feature in the dashboard?” (N=340), 51% report not having used the dashboard. Only 4% report having used it systematically, 6% report 4-6 times and about 20% report having used it once and 20% 2-3 times. On the question “Did your teacher use data from the dashboard in class?” (N=191), 29% of students report that their teacher didn’t use it at all, 62% report that their teacher sometimes used it and 9% report the teacher using it often. For both questions, an important variation is observed over the different courses, again reflecting a range of practices and contexts.

More interesting is the relationship between the use of the dashboard by students and the use of data from the dashboard in class by teachers (as reported by students), as illustrated by *Fig. 2*. The use of data from the dashboard by the teacher in class has a significant positive impact on student’s use of the dashboard, $\text{Chi}^2(8, N=190) = 21.7, p < .01$. But, as illustrated by *Fig. 3*, being asked by the teacher to use the dashboard has an even more significant and positive impact on student’s use of the dashboard, $\text{Chi}^2(16, N=347) = 263.3, p < .001$. This tends to confirm our hypotheses from previous sections about the role of the teacher in students’ use of the dashboard.

We also asked students to indicate what they learned from using the dashboard and the reason(s) why they eventually stopped using it. For both questions they could select one or more options. 46% of respondent selected at least one option representing something they learned from using the dashboard. The most selected option overall (42%) is the identification of recurrent difficulties, which reflects well the purpose of the dashboard. We looked at what the students who report learning from using the dashboard mention as reasons for stopping to use the dashboard. As *Fig. 6* illustrates quite clearly, making a habit of logging their work into the dashboard, thus changing their practices for the long term, seem to be a major difficulty even for students who feel that they learn something useful from using the tool. The perceived worthwhileness of using the dashboard, its integration into the pedagogy of the course and the specificity of the feedback it provides come far after. It is worth mentioning that, of the students who report having used the dashboard, more than 70% found the dashboard easy or very easy to use, only about 9% reported difficulties (N=326).

6 DISCUSSION

We have shown that SRL dashboards can provide both students and teachers with insight on the learning process happening in STEM classrooms, more specifically when students work on solving problems. While the potential benefits of such tools are clear, the results presented above illustrate that some factors play an important role on their impact on the actual practice of its users.

On the teacher side, we have seen that despite a high motivation and active technological and pedagogical support, integrating a new tool into teaching practices is certainly no easy bet. We believe that reallocating class time to include pedagogical interventions - even “just” instructing students to use the tool and giving feedback to the class regularly - is an adoption barrier, but this would have to be further studied.

On the student side, we have shown that participation is particularly affected by a) an active encouragement of the teacher to log data into the learning diary and b) the use by the teacher of information extracted from the dashboard to give feedback to the class. This finding illustrates how, when seen as embedded in a social context, practices are performed in social settings and interlock with the practices of others. While SRL and LADs research focus on how the learners can change their own practice, it does not ask how their practices interact with the practices of teachers or other learners and how changing one part of this system of interrelated practices may impact upon other parts. This particular aspect should be further researched.

Our study also tends to show that, while logging data into the diary is part of the learning process for students, recurrent use is difficult to induce (all the more when the amount of data to log is important) and even more difficult to transform into a habit. We think that this is an important point to take into account in the design of the pedagogical interventions by teachers around such a tool.

Based on these observations, we would recommend that at least instructions to log data in the diary should be embedded regularly into the lessons or exercise sessions and, when possible, logging could be made part of the in-class activities (with the limitation that it could increase barriers for adoption by teacher). Since feedback to the class has an important impact, specific support by teaching assistants could be put in place to multiply feedback opportunities. In the case of an important number of exercises associated to the course, only a subset should probably be selected for logging to limit the impact on motivation.

There are limitations to this study. The relatively low student survey response rates is one of them. Additional qualitative data (e.g. interviews or focus groups) would help us better understand the barriers to a greater engagement from the majority of the students, as well as the advantages classes with high engagement have seen from using the tool more frequently. On the teacher side, the informal feedback during the semester has been very positive – for instance, in one of our many exchanges, one of the teachers has told us: “It is interesting to have this feedback on the exercises. I usually ask the question to the assistants and normally they tell me that everything is fine and that students have no particular difficulties“. However, we could formally evaluate teachers’ opinion on the use of the tool through a focus group for instance. Much analysis work remains to be done on the rich usage dataset generated by the experiment. Among the many possible analyses of interest, we intend to look at the evolution of use over time, the correlation of use with

academic achievement or the students' text responses when they have self-reported problem solving difficulties.

7 CONCLUSION

This paper has presented results from the deployment of a learning analytics dashboard targeting the development of student self-regulated learning in the context of problem solving. Designed taking into account evidence on teaching and learning in STEM Higher Education, this tool has been deployed effectively during one semester in several large-class introductory Maths, Physics and Chemistry courses in the first year of the Engineering bachelor of a Swiss technical university. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the impact of this tool on the practices of its users, namely students and teachers, by looking at their use and opinion on the tool. Drawing on both usage and survey data, we have shown that: a) integrating a new tool into their teaching practice can be a difficulty even for highly motivated teachers; b) the way the teachers integrate the tool into their teaching by prompting students to use it and giving feedback to the class has an important impact on student participation and c) changing their habits is a major obstacle for students to persist in using such a tool on the long term. Perspectives include additional analysis on the usage dataset generated by the study as well as additional qualitative data collection. We intend to continue the development of the dashboard with the addition of other features, in particular to facilitate its integration into the social context in which it is used.

REFERENCES

- [1] Jonassen, D., Strobel, J. and Lee, C. B. (2006), Everyday Problem Solving in Engineering: Lessons for Engineering Educators, *Journal of Engineering Education* Vol. 95, No. 2, pp. 139–151
- [2] Schoenfeld, A. H. (1992), Learning to think mathematically: Problem solving, metacognition, and sense making in mathematics. Handbook of research on mathematics teaching and learning: A project of the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics, Macmillan Publishing Co, Inc, New York, NY, England, pp. 334–370
- [3] Schoenfeld, A. H. (2013), Reflections on Problem Solving Theory and Practice, *TME* Vol. 10, No. 1, pp. 9–34
- [4] Nicol, D. J. and Macfarlane-Dick, D. (2006), Formative assessment and self-regulated learning: a model and seven principles of good feedback practice, *Studies in Higher Education* Vol. 31, No. 2, pp. 199–218
- [5] Lovett, M. C. (2013), Make exams worth more than grades: Using exam wrappers to promote metacognition. Using reflection and metacognition to improve student learning: accross the disciplines, accross the academy, M. Kaplan, N. Silver, D. LaVaque-Manty, D. Meizlish

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- [6] Schmitz, B. and Perels, F. (2011), Self-monitoring of self-regulation during math homework behaviour using standardized diaries, *Metacognition and Learning* Vol. 6, No. 3, pp. 255–273
 - [7] Schwendimann, B. A., Rodríguez-Triana, M. J., Vozniuk, A., Prieto, L. P., Boroujeni, M. S., Holzer, A., Gillet, D. and Dillenbourg, P. (2017), Perceiving Learning at a Glance: A Systematic Literature Review of Learning Dashboard Research, *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies* Vol. 10, No. 1, pp. 30–41
 - [8] Broeck, L. V. den, Laet, T. D., Lacante, M., Pinxten, M., Soom, C. V. and Langie, G. (2018), Predicting the academic achievement of students bridging to engineering: the role of academic background variables and diagnostic testing, *Journal of Further and Higher Education* Vol. 0, No. 0, pp. 1–19
 - [9] Bodily, R. and Verbert, K. (2017), Review of Research on Student-Facing Learning Analytics Dashboards and Educational Recommender Systems, *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies* Vol. 10, No. 4, pp. 405–418
 - [10] Zimmerman, B. J. (2000), Attaining self-regulation: A Social Cognitive Perspective. Handbook of self-regulation, Academic, M. Boekaerts, P. R. Pintrich and M. Zeidners, San Diego, CA
 - [11] Hattie, J., Biggs, J. and Purdie, N. (1996), Effects of Learning Skills Interventions on Student Learning: A Meta-Analysis, *Review of Educational Research* Vol. 66, No. 2, pp. 99–136
 - [12] Panadero, E., Klug, J. and Järvelä, S. (2016), Third wave of measurement in the self-regulated learning field: when measurement and intervention come hand in hand, *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research* Vol. 60, No. 6, pp. 723–735
 - [13] Hattie, J. (2009), Visible learning: a synthesis of over 800 meta-analyses relating to achievement, Routledge, London ; New York